

EOSC-Life

EOSC-Life: Building a digital space for the life sciences

D7.1 – Initial EOSC-LS Cloud Observatory Report

WP7 – Cloud Deployment Services

Lead Beneficiary: EMBL-EBI and Charité

WP leaders: Steven Newhouse and Harald Wagener

Contributing partner(s): EMBL-EBI, Charité, ERINHA, Masaryk University, CSC, and CNR

Authors of this deliverable: **S. Newhouse, H. Wagener, M. González Ferreiro, O. Fano-Bilbao, T. Wildish, M. Dieckmann, A. Niewielska, S. Kapoor, T. Nyrönen**

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Executive Summary

EOSC-LS Cloud Observatory Report

The report details the support mechanism available to the Biological and Medical ESFRI research infrastructures (BMS RIs) and how the allocated cloud resources have been used so far by the BMS Host Institutions (BMS HIs). We analyse the activities carried on to date within the Work Package 7 (WP7) tasks:

- T.7.1 Cloud Resource Planning and Integration
- T.7.2 Cloud Training Programme
- T.7.3 Sensitive Data Hosting and Processing Policy Framework
- T.7.4 Managed Platforms for Data Analysis
- T.7.5 Operations and Support Helpdesk

and provide our point of view on how the WP7 work will evolve during the rest of the project.

Project Objectives

The goal of WP7 is to provide a set of integrated cloud resources to support the cloud based FAIR RI data resources (WP1), workflows (WP2) and science demonstrators (WP3) that are being supported within the project. Through the provided cloud resources, this WP also promotes the implementation and adoption of cloud interoperability standards to ensure EOSC cloud providers are compatible with life-science services and with each other.

With this deliverable, the WP7 has contributed to the following objectives:

- a. Provide an integrated set of public sector community cloud providers appearing in the EOSC Service Catalogue with access managed using the LS AAI (WP5) - Task 7.1
- b. Procure commercial cloud providers using a cloud procurement framework (e.g. HNSciCloud or GEANT) that are integrated with the LS AAI and appear in the EOSC Service Catalogue. - Task 7.1
- c. Allocate resources from the supported EOSC-Life cloud providers in the EOSC Service Catalogue to the selected workflows and demonstrators from the EOSC-Life project, and compensate the cloud providers for the usage made at the agreed rates and mechanisms approved by European (H2020) projects. - Task 7.1
- d. Provide a technical support and consultancy function that will work with the selected demonstrators and workflows to support their deployment onto the allocated cloud resources to eventually establish a sustainable ResOps “Community of Practice” for cloud-enabled workflows. - Task 7.2 and 7.5
- e. Establish a set of quantifiable capabilities needed for the secure hosting of sensitive data and identify which of the supported cloud providers in the EOSC Service Catalogue have these characteristics. - Task 7.3
- f. The implementation of the principles for a secure and trusted cloud will be implemented in cooperation with WP4 which will collect the requirements for the BMS RI so that cloud

- solutions offered for the storage and computation of human research data comply with the legal requirements for sensitive data. - Task 7.3
- g. Data access controls for sensitive data on cloud target systems are enforced in collaboration with WP5, and leverage technologies (e.g. OAuth2 based implementation) from previous projects (CORBEL and EXCELERATE). - Task 7.3
 - h. Provide deployable platforms for e.g. Galaxy and CWL based workflows (using GA4GH Cloud-WG compatible service). - Task 7.4

Detailed Report on the Deliverable

The report details the support mechanism available to the BMS RIs and how the allocated cloud resources have been used so far by the BMS RIs. To do so, we analyse the activities carried on to date within the WP7 tasks.

Activities on Cloud Resource Planning and Integration

Task 7.1 is led by Steven Newhouse (EMBL-EBI) with contributions from the team at EMBL-EBI (Susheel Varma, Montse Gonzalez and Oihane Fano-Bilbao) and feedback from across the Work Package and project.

Background

The purpose of this task is to establish a transparent process by which requests for cloud resources coming from across the project (primarily WP1, WP2 and WP3) can be allocated to a set of cloud service providers internal and external to the project.

Description of the work accomplished

The initial focus during the first year was to establish the EOSC-Life WP7 Resource Allocation Process (RAP)¹ by which cloud requirements from across the project could be received and reviewed, before being allocated to the most appropriate cloud service provider. The RAP team is accessed through eosc-life-wp7-rap@elixir-europe.org and will initially ask requestors to submit their request through a form² which captures all relevant information to support the review. Following successful technical review and feedback, the activity will be allocated to a cloud provider.

EOSC-Life is able to access a variety of cloud service providers from within and external to the project. Internally, cloud service providers are expected to appear in the EOSC Service Catalogue³ under

¹ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Z0Izwh8vafqMZ8R6dDmIQgvjRxsF3IZMjl65s3m2xL4/edit?usp=sharing>

² <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1IEf3HMbULAiXZ6zLGsCKj3SLs37enq1ud4Do3E5efaM/edit>

³ https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/c/compute?research_areas-filter=&research_areas-all=&providers-filter=&providers-all=&target_groups-all=&related_platforms-filter=&related_platforms-all=&related_platforms%5B%5D=15&rating=&location=

(currently) the ELIXIR and eventually the 'EOSC Life' tag. Collaboration has also been established with the Open Clouds for Research in Europe (OCRE) project which will be providing cloud resources that can be used for payment and some additional support for moving applications to cloud providers.

Two requests for resources have been received so far and these are for relatively minor quantities of resources.

Next steps

The results of the work in Year 1 are now being implemented as part of the Open Calls for 'cloudification' of data resources (WP1) and further demonstrators (WP3). The principles established in the WP7 review process will be embedded into the relevant WP1 and WP3 evaluation procedures.

Activities on Cloud Training Programme

Task 7.2 is led by Tony Wildish (EMBL-EBI) and Marius Dieckmann (ELIXIR-DE), with contributions from the EMBL-EBI Cloud Consultants (David Yuan, CD Tiwari, and Soumyadip De) & CSC's Cloud specialists (Shubham Kapoor, Juhani Kataja & Kalle Happonen).

Background

The purpose of this task is to provide the scientific community with the knowledge they need to make effective and efficient use of cloud technologies. Many scientists have plenty of experience of HPC computing with large in-house batch clusters, but do not know how to translate that experience into computing in the cloud.

There is a lot of professional, high-quality material available for people who want to learn cloud computing in depth, normally specific to individual cloud providers. Rather than try to duplicate that material, this task aims to introduce the basic concepts, using examples drawn from the scientific research environment that the users are familiar with, and in a way that can translate readily across commercial, private and RI cloud infrastructures.

The key requirements are that the material be tuned for the audience, that the course be available for standalone study, as well as being suitable for a classroom, and that the course be easy to maintain. Cloud training materials will be made available on-line with the EOSC-Life WP9 (e.g. using ELIXIR Training platform TeSS service⁴). It is expected that WP7 will deliver this course at least once a year which will be recorded by WP11 for distribution alongside the self-paced course material through TeSS.

Description of the work accomplished

The EMBL-EBI Cloud Consultants have provided a 'ResOps course'⁵, covering the use of containers built with Docker, continuous integration/deployment with Gitlab, and an introduction to Kubernetes. The

⁴ <https://tess.elixir-europe.org>

⁵ <https://bit.ly/resops-2019>

course exercises were run on an Openstack tenancy in the EMBL-EBI Embassy cloud, with each student being given their own virtual machine. The exercises could just as easily be run on other cloud providers, or on a laptop.

The ResOps course has been given several times at EMBL-EBI during 2019, to EOSC-Life WP1 in Berlin in November 2019, and as a remote-attendance course to the BioExcel2 project in February 2020. In all, about 180 people attended the course. Feedback has been positive, with most attendees agreeing that they would recommend the course to colleagues.

The German network for bioinformatics infrastructure (de.NBI) held on-hands training sessions on Kubernetes and cloud computing in general during its annual cloud user meetings in 2018 and 2019.

In 2019, ELIXIR-FI (CSC) also provided a portfolio of cloud training courses on IaaS cloud (OpenStack)⁶ and PaaS Cloud (Kubernetes/OKD)⁷. Courses were well received by life sciences participants.

Next steps

The ResOps course will be made available as a set of standalone videos and exercises, suitable for study by individuals or groups in a non-classroom setting, or for use in a scheduled course.

de.NBI and EMBL-EBI are now also collaborating on an advanced Kubernetes training course, building on from the material of the two basic courses. This will be a one-day remote attendance event, with all the presentations recorded, so it can be taken offline by future participants. This course will be ready for delivery in September 2020.

Activities on Sensitive Data Hosting and Processing Policy Framework

This task is led by Harald Wagener (BIH, Germany) with contributions from WP7 and WP4 members, namely Chris Lawrenz, Willem van Boiten and Christian Ohmann.

Background

Objective of the task is to support users to find cloud providers that are able to meet their sensitive data processing requirements and are able to offer the capabilities expected of research infrastructure and services so there is an assurance to the user and the data owners that the cloud infrastructure and services can be used to host and process sensitive data for research and analytics.

Description of the work accomplished

A questionnaire has been developed to allow cloud providers to go through a self-assessment. The result of that self-assessment aims to provide end users a selection of cloud providers that meet their

⁶ <https://www.csc.fi/fi/web/training/-/pouta-cloud-course-2019>

⁷ <https://www.csc.fi/fi/web/training/-/fundamentals-of-container-clouds-with-rahti>

expectations about environments they process sensitive data in. The questionnaire went through two rounds of review and revision so far.

Link to the current document:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1751i2qj0NJZnoDuVXEOLb8mT_80AiKeMulaMT2iXBUs/edit

Next steps

Next steps are

- a) Finalization of the questionnaire and making it available to cloud providers so they can do the self assessment and give feedback on the questionnaire.
- b) Looking into integration with the WP4 toolbox

Activities on Managed Platforms for Data Analysis

This activity is led by Shubham Kapoor (CSC, Finland) and for most of year 1 by Susheel Varma and now Ania Niewielska (EMBL-EBI). Additional contributions have come from the Software Development & Operations team at EMBL-EBI (Ania Niewielska, Thiago Albuquerque, Cibin Sadasivan Baby and others), Cloud Specialists at CSC (Álvaro González, Kalle Happonen, Jarno Latinen & others) and ELIXIR-DE (Marius Dieckmann, Sven Twardziok & others).

Background

The purpose of this task is to design and develop workflow execution platforms that can be deployed onto EOSC cloud infrastructure and offered to users as per managed Platform as a Service (PaaS) or in some cases as per Software as a Service (SaaS) models.

Workflow execution platform developed as per this task will be leveraging from global standards emerging from the GA4GH community. Users of the Workflow Platform will be able to create portable workflows in languages such as CWL using tools packaged as containers and send those workflows for execution to Workflow Platform installations. The choice of execution environment will be primarily driven by data locality, availability of resources and the cost of compute.

The joined community effort around developing GA4GH-Compatible Workflow Platform is being further complimented by the ELIXIR Cloud and AAI Project⁸, which aims at establishing a federated cloud computing network across European e-infrastructures by enabling the analysis of population-scale genomic and phenotypic data across participating international nodes and has in turn been now regarded as one of the GA4GH Driver Projects.

⁸ <https://elixir-europe.github.io/cloud/>

Description of the work accomplished

The managed workflow platform is still in development and the biggest effort is being put into transforming a successful Proof of Concept (PoC) into a production ready system.

Some of the recent developments include:

- **New components:** A new WebPortal (CWLab)⁹ has been created that can serve as a user interface for GA4GH-WES and has been integrated with cwl-wes. The WebPortal supports user authentication via ELIXIR AAI & is successfully deployed in the deNbi cloud.
- **DevOps improvements:** HELM charts have been created for cwl-wes (a GA4GH WES wrapper around CWL workflow executions) and TESK (Kubernetes execution backend) allowing *one-liner* deployments of these services by cloud admins.
- **Enhanced integration options:**
 - The support for a shared file system has been implemented in TESK, which extends the list of supported file systems/file transfer solutions to: FTP, HTTP and shared file system.
 - The work has started on enabling the support for alternative workflow description languages than CWL (WDL, Nextflow)
- **New Deployments:** New TES endpoints of the platform have been successfully deployed at cloud infrastructures of ELIXIR-CZ & ELIXIR-GR. Currently platform has its TES endpoints deployed in CSC Finland, EMBL-EBI, ELIXIR-CZ, ELIXIR-GR and ELIXIR-IT.

The current use of the Platform is limited to test installations and demonstration workflow runs. Nevertheless, the presence of the Platform at multiple events generates considerable interest and the community around the initiative is growing.

The Platform has been present at:

- ELIXIR AHM 2019 and 2020
- GA4GH Plenary 2019 and 2020 (upcoming)
- ELIXIR BioHackaton 2019 and 2020 (upcoming)
- Google Summer of Code 2019 and 2020 (ongoing)

The Platform has demonstrated execution of real life scientific workflows namely :

- Rare Diseases Workflow, setup includes execution of workflow on the existing platform with or without FEGA integration.
- Multiple Sequence Alignment workflow for comparing Covid19 surface glycoprotein.
- Marine Metagenomics (MMTESP) workflow.

Finally, Elixir Cloud & AAI project members are actively contributing to the development of GA4GH standards and have been acting as spec champions of TRS and TES standards.

⁹ <https://cwlabs.krini.ingress.rancher.computational.bio/>

Next steps

The following steps are:

1. Developing the existing platform further from PoC stage towards production state.
 - a. Adding S3 compatible object store support for large data sets.
 - b. Scalability of platform to handle large simultaneous workflows.
 - c. Building CI/CD pipelines for the platform services.
2. Enabling support for new workflow languages (WDL, Nextflow, etc.) & workflow engines (Cromwell, Nextflow etc.).
3. Adding support of intelligent workflow federation logics via proWES service for ex. based on data locality, compute wait times, costs etc.
4. Maintaining the platform compliant to latest GA4GH Cloud (WES¹⁰, TES¹¹, TRS¹² & DRS¹³) & DURIE (GA4GH Passports & Visas¹⁴) WS standards.

Activities on Operations and Support Help desk

Task 7.5 is led by Montserrat González Ferreiro (EMBL-EBI) with the collaboration of all WP7 and especially Matej Antol (MU) and Alexandr Kolovratnik (MU).

Background

The technical operation for individual cloud resources is provided outside the EOSC-Life project but the operation and support of the EOSC-Life infrastructure as a whole are supported through task 7.5. Operations and Support Helpdesk. The task involves providing a support help desk and a monitoring system for key services.

These are the requirements for the support help desk:

- It should be accessible by end-users from WP1, WP2, WP3, and cloud providers from within the BMS RIs.
- It should bring together experts in cloud deployment and cloud operation to help integrate cloud providers into the EOSC infrastructure and to support end-users and data experts as they deploy their workloads.
- It should provide the demonstrators selected in WP3 access consultancy support as they start planning their cloud deployment. This consultancy support is provided by technical staff participating in WP7.
- It should establish ticket queues in an existing helpdesk technology (e.g. Request Tracker) to support task 7.5 and potentially other WPs within the project.

¹⁰ <https://github.com/ga4gh/workflow-execution-service-schemas>

¹¹ <https://github.com/ga4gh/task-execution-schemas>

¹² <https://github.com/ga4gh/tool-registry-service-schemas>

¹³ <https://github.com/ga4gh/data-repository-service-schemas>

¹⁴ https://github.com/ga4gh-duri/ga4gh-duri.github.io/tree/master/researcher_ids

These are the requirements for the monitoring system:

- Monitor any key services (e.g. data transfer) to ensure their continued operation and performance.

Description of the work accomplished

Work accomplished	Objective	Date
Discovery survey to WP7 on services, contacts, monitoring, and training	The survey helped WP7 identify all the information needed to start developing task 7.5.	Jul 2019
Define the WP7 procedure to handle incidents and service requests	The procedure allows WP7 to handle incidents and service requests in a common and standardised way.	Jul 2019
Define the configuration of the Request Tracker (RT) queue to provide help desk support	The definition of access, triaging, notifications and standard replies facilitate the implementation of the RT queue.	Jul 2019
Setting up an RT queue in the Masaryk University ticketing system	After surveying different options, the helpdesk queue was agreed to be managed and hosted by MU due to their experience hosting the helpdesk support for the ELIXIR AAI. EMBL-EBI defined the configuration considering the requirements and information provided by the WP7. MU implemented the queue and configuration to make the help desk service possible.	Jul 2019
MS17: Establish the Operations and Support Helpdesk	The helpdesk service and contact eosc-life-helpdesk@elixir-europe.org was announced to the whole EOSC-Life community. The privacy notice for the RT queue was pending to be approved.	Aug 2019
Setting up the Privacy Notice for the Helpdesk support queue	A proposal was made by EMBL-EBI in Jul 2019 and discussed with MU, as hosts of the ticketing system, and ELIXIR, as coordinators of EOSC-Life. The selected	Nov 2019

	privacy notice was added later to the RT queue footer and from then on all the users know how their personal data is processed.	
Survey to WP7 on services ready to be offered or ready to be developed	It helped to know what services are offered to WP3 (and helped with the RAP) as well as provided us with information on the key services to monitor. WP7 shared this information with all the WPs in March 2020 (See Appendix).	Jan 2020
Update the WP7 Procedure to handle incidents and service requests	The procedure was updated with simplifications and diagrams that reflect the new changes in triaging and facilitate the help desk work.	Jul 2020
Fine-tune the Request Tracker queue at Masaryk University	During 2020 EMBL-EBI and MU discussed and implemented improvements in the triage mechanism. Also kept the access to the relevant people updated (joiners/leavers), and explored the possibility to provide a joint help desk service with WP5 but the offer was declined. EMBL-EBI and MU keep the Request Tracker queue configuration updated and review it periodically to make it as efficient as possible.	Ongoing

Next steps

During the first part of the project, we have focussed on providing the help desk solution to provide a unique contact point to the EOSC-Life service users. The next steps will be to keep the help desk updated and adapted to any new needs from the project and work on the monitoring of the key services provided by WP7.

Abbreviations

AAI - Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 824087.

BMS RI - Biological and Medical Research Infrastructures
BMS HI - Biological and Medical Host Institutions
CI/CD - Continuous Integration and Continuous Delivery/Deployment
CWL - Common Workflow Language
DRS - Data Repository Service
DURI - Data Use & Researcher Identities
EOSC - European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI - European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR - Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
FEGA - Federated European Genome-Phenome Archive
FTP - File Transfer Protocol
GA4GH - The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
HTTP - Hypertext Transfer Protocol
LS - Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
PaaS - Platform as a Service
PoC - Proof of Concept
RAP - Resource Allocation Process
RI - Research Infrastructure
RT - Request Tracker
SaaS - Software as a Service
SDO - Software Development and Operations
SLA - Service Level Agreements
TESK - Task Execution Service
TeSS - Training e-Support System
TRS - Tool Registry Service
WDL - Web Development Language
WES - Workflow Execution Service
WP - Work Package
WS - Web Services
WPL - Work Package Leaders

Delivery and Schedule

The delivery is delayed:

No

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 824087.

Adjustments

Adjustments made:

None

Appendices

Appendix 1: Operations and Support Helpdesk procedure

1. Overview and context

Procedure ID	EOSC-life-PROC-WP7-0001
Procedure name	EOSC-life Operations and support helpdesk
Procedure's purpose	EOSC-life WP7 provides the operation and support of the EOSC-LS infrastructure. End-users from WP1/WP2/WP3, and cloud providers from within the BMS RIs are able to request support through a helpdesk that will follow this procedure to operate.
Services to what this procedure applies	The services provided by WP7: e-infra CZ , ecp , cPouta , ePouta , rahti , wes-elixir , tesk , embassy , denbi, denbi-Galaxy, cnr-Galaxy . Here is more information about the services provided by WP7
Key information	<p>The Helpdesk email is: eosc-life-helpdesk@elixir-europe.org</p> <p>The tool to support request tracking is Request Tracker and the RT queue is managed by Masaryk University.</p> <p>The RT web interface is: https://rt.elixir-czech.cz</p> <p>Note that if an organisation providing a service within WP7 has its own ticketing system and would like to track the user request received at eosc-life-helpdesk using it, they will need to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manually copy the ticket to their ticketing system. - Work on it to find a solution. - When it's solved, provide an update in the eosc-life-helpdesk queue and solve the ticket.
Procedure's owner (responsible to keep it updated)	Montserrat González Ferreiro (montserrat@ebi.ac.uk)

Version & change tracking	<p>v1.0 - 21/07/2019 - MGF (EMBI-EBI) - Reviewed draft</p> <p>v1.1 - 22/07/2019 - MGF (EMBI-EBI) - Reviewed draft</p> <p>v1.2 - 01/08/2019 - MGF (EMBI-EBI) - Reviewed draft</p> <p>v1.2 - 07/08/2019 - MGF (EMBI-EBI) - Reviewed draft</p> <p>v1.3 - 26/11/2019 - MGF (EMBI-EBI) - Final version</p> <p>v1.4 - 09/04/2020 - MGF (EMBI-EBI) - Updated version</p> <p>v1.5 - 07/07/2020 - MGF (EMBI-EBI) - Updated version</p>
Storage location	<p>https://docs.google.com/document/d/1gqp4LR_Zf9mNsMUT_QeyA7z2tQUTogGFOLONksD_Yx8/edit</p>

2. Triggers

The execution of this procedure is usually triggered by:

Trigger	Description
A user sends a service request	The user requests information about one or more services offered by EOSC-Life WP7 or requests access to one or more services offered by EOSC-Life WP7.
A user reports an incident	The user has experienced an issue with one or more services provided by the EOSC-Life WP7 and wants to report it and obtain a solution.

3. Steps to be performed

Steps	Description	Actions
Discover user request	The users or potential users of WP7 services send a service request or report an incident by sending an email to eosc-life-helpdesk@elixir-europe.org and a ticket is created in Request Tracker.	A11
Check service request of incident	The WP7 team check the ticket the RT web interface https://rt.elixir-czech.cz Log-in using your credentials. You will see a list of RT queues, you will only have access to the eosc-life-helpdesk queue. Click on it and you will see the list of tickets.	A1, A2, A3, A4

	<p>The service request or incident report should include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A short description - How has the incident been detected (By using the service? Through monitoring?) - What is/are the affected service/s <p>Based on the service that we think the ticket makes reference to, a member of WP7 will ask clarifications to the user that created the ticket.</p>	
<p>Assign ticket owner and change the ticket status to open and identify service</p>	<p>A ticket owner will be assigned considering the service to what the ticket makes reference to. Select “Owner” and assign an owner from the list. The ticket will be open, so the ticket owner will go to “Actions” and select “Reply” and select “Status” as “Open” (or to any status as needed).</p> <p>Select “Service EOSC services” and assign a service from the list. The list includes: ecp, cPouta, ePouta, rahti, wes-elixir, tesk, embassy, denbi, denbi-Galaxy, cnr-Galaxy, security, and data-protection.</p> <p>The CF will be used in the following way:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ecp: for queries related to EBI Cloud Portal. ● cPouta: for queries related to cPouta. ● ePouta: for queries related to ePouta. ● rahti: for queries related to Rahti. ● wes-elixir: for queries related to WES-ELIXIR. ● tesk: for queries related to Tesk. ● embassy: for queries related to the Embassy cloud. 	<p>A5</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● denbi: for queries related to denbi-iaaS, denbi-PaaS, denbi-WaaS, denbi-SaaS, denbi-CaaS ● denbi-Galaxy: for queries related to denbi-Galaxy. ● cnr-Galaxy: for queries related to cnr-Galaxy. ● security: for queries related to IT security when the service to which the query is related to can not be identified. ● data-protection: for queries related to data protection. <p>More custom fields will be added whenever we have new requirements (e.g. if more services become available).</p>	
<p>Work on the ticket</p>	<p>The team will work on the answer/solution to the request.</p> <p>Higher priority should be given to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IT security incidents and questions, - data protection incidents and questions, and - technical incidents. <p>Requests for information and service requests should be treated as business as usual.</p> <p>It is the responsibility of the organisation providing the service to adequately escalate and solve any IT security incident, data protection query and technical incident.</p> <p>Optional: If an organisation providing a service within WP7 has its own ticketing system and they would like to track the user request received at eosclife-helpdesk, they will need to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manually copy the ticket to their RT system. - Work on it to find a solution. - When it's solved, provide an update in the eosclife-helpdesk queue and solve the ticket. 	<p>A6</p>
<p>Solve the ticket</p>	<p>The request is solved and the user is informed of it. The ticket owner needs to write an answer to the user and inform them about the ticket status.</p> <p>We'll use the different status tags:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stalled: the request cannot be solved at the moment. - Resolved: the request has been solved. - Rejected: the request is not addressed to the EOSC-Life WP7 or doesn't fit in the scope of the helpdesk. - Deleted: the request was created by mistake and after discussing it with the user, it will be deleted. 	<p>A7</p>

	<p>Whatever the ticket status is, the requester needs to keep informed on how the work is progressing.</p> <p>It is recommended to send this message when a request has been solved to prevent having tickets reopened:</p> <p><i>“Dear requester, This ticket will be closed since we consider it has been solved. Please, do not respond to this email if you do not want to reopen the ticket and you agree with the given solution. Thank you, EOSC-life WP7 team”</i></p>	
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4. Additional information

4.1. How to request/revoke access to the RT queue

In July 2019 we requested the teams providing services to EOSC-Life to let us know who will need access to the RT queue (see the [list](#)).

If you need to request/revoke access to the RT queue, please send an email to Matej Antol (antol@ics.muni.cz) and Alexandr Kolovratnik (kolovratnik@ics.muni.cz) telling them the name and email address of the person needing/not needing access to the RT queue for the EOSC-Life helpdesk and they will provide you the suitable instructions to follow.

4.2. Auto reply message template

The auto reply template will be implemented to use in the WP7 helpdesk RT queue. The rest of the templates (owner change, transaction, correspondence, admin correspondence, admin comment, ownerChangeNotifyAdminCcs, queue change, forward, and forward ticket) will be the ones used in RT by default and they will inform factually of the actions happening. E.g. if correspondence is added to the ticket, the notification will say “correspondence has been added”.

The auto reply template is:

“Thank you for contacting us.

Your query has been assigned an id of [eosc-life-helpdesk #NNNNN]. Please include this string in any related emails. We will be in contact with you as soon as possible.

Kind regards,

EOSC-life WP7 Operations and Support Helpdesk

eosc-life-helpdesk@elixir-europe.org

Find information on how we process your personal data in the EOSC-Life helpdesk privacy notice”

4.3. Footer to apply to all the responses to support requests (includes a link to the privacy notice)

Kind regards,

EOSC-life WP7 Operations and Support Helpdesk

eosc-life-helpdesk@elixir-europe.org

Find information on how we process your personal data in the EOSC-Life helpdesk privacy notice”

4.4. Privacy notice

The privacy notice for EOSC-Life Helpdesk is published here: <https://it.muni.cz/en/services/it-servicedesk/eosc-life-helpdesk-privacy-notice>

4.5. Notifications in the helpdesk RT queue

Condition	Action	Template	Status
On Correspond	Open Tickets	Blank	Off
On Owner Change	Notify Owner & AdminCcs	Owner Change	On
On Create	Autoreply To Requestors	Autoreply	On
On Create	Notify AdminCcs	Transaction	On
On Correspond	Notify Requestors and Ccs	Correspondence	On
On Correspond	Notify Other Recipients	Correspondence	On
On Transaction	Extract Subject Tag	Blank	On
On Correspond	Notify Owner & AdminCcs	Admin Correspondence	On
On Comment	Notify Owner & AdminCcs as Comment	Admin Comment	On
On Correspond	User Defined	Blank	Off
On Owner Change	Notify AdminCcs	OwnerChangeNotifyAdminCcs	On
On Queue Change	Notify AdminCcs	Queue Change	Off
On Transaction	On SetStarted Open Ticket	Blank	On
On Forward Transaction	Send Froward	Forward	On
On Forward Ticket	Send Forward	Forward Ticket	On
On Queue Change	Notify Requestors	Queue Change	Off

Appendix 2: Software & Managed Platform Services Available by March 2020

1. European Galaxy Server

The [European Galaxy Server](https://usegalaxy.eu) (usegalaxy.eu) is provided by the University of Freiburg (ELIXIR DE) in cooperation with many other ELIXIR nodes.

It offers more than 2000 tools, more than 100 reference genomes, supports ELIXIR AAI and is open to all researchers. This service is using the ELIXIR-DE cloud and various resources provided by European partners.

Reproducible tool deployments are offered via conda packages and/or containers via ([Bioconda](#), [conda-forge](#) and [BioContainers](#)) with shared and mirrored, cross-community reference data sets (genomes, indices, databases), using more than 30.000 containers in a distributed infrastructure using [CVMFS](#).

Training

If you are planning to offer training in Galaxy, you can request dedicated infrastructure resources to conduct your training via the Training Infrastructure as a Service (TaaS).

Engage with us in the development of new services using Galaxy

User communities can collaborate with us to build services like <https://proteomics.usegalaxy.eu>, <https://metagenomics.usegalaxy.eu> or <https://climate.usegalaxy.eu> with dedicated tools, workflows and own support channels, using a shared infrastructure across Europe.

Contact

Björn Grüning (bjoern.gruening@gmail.com)

2. Chipster

Chipster, provided by CSC (ELIXIR-FI), is a user-friendly software for analyzing high-throughput data such as RNA-seq and single cell RNA-seq. It contains over 450 analysis tools and a large collection of reference genomes. Users can save and share automatic analysis workflows, and visualize data interactively using for example the [built-in genome browser](#). CSC offers two interfaces to Chipster: [Java Web Start client](#) and [Web App](#). The former is also available in [EOSC marketplace](#). Chipster is [open source](#), and the server environment is available as a [virtual machine image](#) and a CVMFS repository. The cloud-native Web App is installed with Helm chart and runs in Kubernetes container clouds.

Training

CSC organises [training on different data analysis topics](#) using Chipster. [Course materials](#) complete with slides, exercises, lecture videos and course data are freely available, and free training accounts are offered on CSC's Chipster server. Users can also get familiar with Chipster by following tutorial videos on [Chipster's YouTube channel](#).

Contact

CSC Service Desk (servicedesk@csc.fi) and Chipster team (chipster@csc.fi)

3. REMS

The Resource Entitlement Management System provided by CSC (ELIXIR FI) is a tool for managing access rights to resources, such as research datasets. You can see the available resources visiting <https://github.com/CSCfi/remis/> and understand better how to Authorise access to sensitive data watching this video <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XXOph-0wacc>

Contact

CSC Service Desk (servicedesk@csc.fi)

4. ELIXIR AAI

The ELIXIR Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI), provided by CSC (ELIXIR FI) and ELIXIR CZ, enables researchers to use their home organisation credentials or community or commercial identities (e.g. ORCID, LinkedIn) to sign in and access data and services they need. It also allows service providers (both in academia and industry) to control and manage access rights of their users and create different access levels for research groups or international projects.

For example, two different researchers in the same university may be working on different European or national research projects and may need access to completely different data or compute resources. ELIXIR AAI ensures that they can access the right resources, using their university credentials, while making sure they can't see each others' data.

Training

Visit <https://elixir-europe.org/events/past-webinars> to discover webinars such as [ELIXIR Webinar: Access to Sensitive Human Data with the ELIXIR AAI](#), [ELIXIR Webinar: de.NBI Cloud Integration to ELIXIR AAI](#), [Use of AAI for the ELIXIR Intranet and access to ELIXIR services](#).

Contact

CSC Service Desk (servicedesk@csc.fi)

5. Platform as a Service (PaaS)

Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin (de.NBI) provides workflow execution platforms in accordance with standards set by [GA4GH](#) for users of all de.NBI cloud centers. Establishment of Kubernetes and virtual cluster deployment is planned in the medium term.

Contact

Chris Lawerenz (christian.lawerenz@bihealth.de)

6. Laniakea

[Laniakea](#), provided by National Research Council - Institute of Biomembranes, Bioenergetics and Molecular Biotechnologies (ELIXIR-IT), offers a platform for the automatic deployment of Galaxy-based virtualized environments through an easy setup procedure, providing an on-demand workspace ready to be used by life scientists and bioinformaticians.

End-users interact with Laniakea through a web front-end that allows them to easily configure and manage each Galaxy instance. The virtual Galaxy instances are customizable in terms of virtual CPUs, RAM and storage through the web dashboard, and deployable with different sets of pre-installed tools. Each instance comes with reference data (e.g. genomic sequences) already available for many species, shared among all the instances. Each Galaxy instance can be automatically linked to an encrypted data storage volume.

Finally, the service is scalable and users can choose among a full range of different computational capabilities: from limited ones to serve e.g. small research groups, Galaxy developers or for didactic and training purposes, to instances with cluster support to handle larger research activities.

Engage with us in the development of new services using Laniakea

Join forces with us to have new Galaxy flavours, i.e. Galaxy tools presets ready to be deployed on-demand with Galaxy, that can be easily developed and [added to Laniakea](#)

Contact

Laniakea team (laniakea.helpdesk@gmail.com)

